

Do we need a new EU Agenda for Cities?

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Our AEIDL Senior Expert on Territorial Development sums up key issues that the forthcoming European Commission plan to support cities could address.

Didn't we have an EU Urban Agenda?

In his [Mission Letter](#) for the 2024-2029 EU Term, Raffaele Fitto, European Commission Vice-President for Cohesion and Reform, sets out that “to harness the potential of cities as innovation, growth, and competitiveness engines, you should put forward an ambitious policy agenda for cities. This agenda should provide a clear vision for the future of cities, looking at issues such as housing, climate action, digitalisation, mobility, social inclusion and equality.”

In his [written reply](#) to his confirmation hearing, Vice President Fitto confirmed that he will “propose a comprehensive Policy Agenda for Cities that provides a clear vision for urban development, defines the EU’s approach to sustainable urban growth, and translates EU priorities into tangible local actions. To ensure that no city is left behind, cities and towns must have ownership and active participation in both policy design and implementation.”

Significant political capital is being invested throughout 2025 in developing this new agenda, starting with a [public consultation](#), the latest [EU Cities Forum](#), and a Communication after the summer.

This policy brief builds on the EU Policy work led by [AEIDL](#) for the [RURBANIVE](#) (*RURal-uRBAN synergies emerged in an immersive innovation ecosystem*), Horizon Europe project, including a [Policy Brief](#) on this topic, together with our the Analysis and mapping of relevant policies at EU level, and our submission on behalf of this and other projects to the public consultation on the [EU’s next long-term budget \(MFF\) – implementing EU funding with Member States and regions](#).

Because this is by no means the first time the EU launches an EU urban agenda this policy brief seeks to address following fundamental questions:

- What is a city?

- A new EU power for cities?
- An agenda for big cities?
- Direct EU Funding for cities?
- A new One-Stop-Shop for cities?

To do so, **15 Strategic Policy options** are put forward that will help address the degree of policy innovation that the new EU Agenda for Cities could provide over the coming years.

Table I: Minimum Thresholds of local authorities in EU programmes and funds

Local Area units (LAU)	3,305 inhabitants (Avg. EU28 2016 LAU 2)
Urban Audit	50.000 inhabitants (LAU)
CLLD	10.000 - 150.000 inhabitants
EU Mission Cities / European Urban Initiative	50.000 inhabitants – 10.000 inhabitants
Sustainable Urban Development	20.000 inhabitants
NGEU (e.g. RRF, Spain)	5.000 inhabitants
ERDF (e.g. POPE, Spain)	10.000 inhabitants – 20.000 inhabitants
Small Urban Areas (SUA)	5.000 – 20.000
Functional Urban Area Of which: Larger Urban Zone (LUZ)	1.500 h/km ² with minimal 50 000 inhabitants. Over 250.000 inhabitants
Functional Rural Areas	50.000 inhabitants and max. 60 minutes access basic services.
Minimal Urban population density (DEGURBA – TERCET – EUROSTAT)	300 inhabitants km ²
Minimal financial Management capacity (EIB)	50 million

Source: Pazos-Vidal (2023)

What is a city?

The EU has shown world leadership by coming up with the [DEGURBA](#) classification, leading to the [first universal definition](#) of a “city” through the OECD and UN. This typology reflects Europe’s diverse urbanisation, unlike other continents, with more polarised urban-rural divides.

However, there’s a gap between analytical classifications and policymaking. Despite the [TERCET](#) classification’s legal standing since 2017, it hasn’t been linked to EU Structural and Investment Funds. Additionally, Table I shows significant diversity in thresholds across various programs, often developed ad hoc, reflecting the plethora of funding instruments and programs.

Integrate DEGURBA and TERCET into a unified framework for EU funding to ensure consistent criteria, better reflect Europe’s diverse urban forms, and to improve the targeting support across urban and rural areas

Prioritising functional area approaches

It is welcome that the consultation document speaks of “core” and “surrounding areas – for access to essential services and for a high quality of life” but it does not explicitly mention functional areas. However this is one of the great innovations of DEGURBA as per [Functional Urban Areas](#) (see table below), and there is growing work on [Functional Rural Areas](#), often centred around small towns to determine accessibility to basic services – though often what they do is identifying deserts of service provision.

Both Functional Urban Areas and Functional Rural Areas must be complementary and should be a requirement for planning EU-funded interventions, including EU Structural and Investment Funds and the European Semester.

Embedding the *rurban* approach

The interlinkages between urban and rural areas, which is explored by RURBANIVE, has quite a long history, most notably the preparatory action, which was led by the Urban Intergroup of the European Parliament, and led to the [rurban preparatory action](#) that in turn led to an OECD report in 2013. However, this approach on urban-rural functionalities is still not fully embedded in policymaking nor a requirement in domestic transposition of structural reforms and EU investments.

The new Agenda for Cities needs to fully embed the *rurban* approach, integrating urban-rural functionalities into policymaking and EU investments.

Has the EU got powers on urban policy?

Rather than being non-existent, the EU competence in urban policy is dispersed. Instead of it being framed in art 4 TFEU as a shared competence, the EU indirectly has a set of powers that, taken together, amount to an exceptionally large set of powers – summarised in Table II.

Table II: EU influence in cities

EUROPEAN UNION	Areas	Main elements
Structural Influence • Subsidiarity Principle • Sincere Cooperation • Internal market	Environmental Legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Impact Assessment Natura 2000 (Birds and Habitats Directives) Urban Waste and Water directives
	Energy Legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Directives (Buildings, Renewables, Energy Efficiency)
	Competition Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State Aid Guidelines Public Procurement Directive (esp. Public-Public cooperation)
Instrumental Influence • Shared Competence • Art 174 TFEU • Shared Management	Cohesion Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural Funds Regulations Partnership Agreements and Regional or Multi-Regional Programmes
	European Territorial Cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INTERREG (cross-border, transnational and interregional) Macroregional Strategies European Groupings of Territorial Cooperation
	Integrated Territorial Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> URBAN Initiatives (c. 2007) JESSICA Integrated territorial investments (ITI) CLLD - 5% LEADER, EAFRD 8% Sustainable Urban Development ERDF Next Generation EU NECP Just Transition Plans Urban mobility observatory – ELTIS Network for cleaner and better transport in cities – CIVITAS Urban access regulations in Europe – Urban Mobility Action Plan – Intelligent Transport Systems Covenant of mayors for climate and energy
Discursive Influence	EU Overarching Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lisbon/ Gothenburg /Europe 2020 Strategies European Semester – PNR, Annex D European Green Deal/ SDGs * / NECP / Just Transition Plans
	EU Territorial Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leipzig Charter – Ljubljana Agreement on Sustainable Cities European Urban Agenda – Pact of Amsterdam (2016 -) Covenant Mayors, Mission Cities Smart Cities and Communities Initiative European Rural Pact Urban Mobility Plan
	EU territorial planning documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European spatial development perspective European Territorial Agenda 2020-2030 Territorial Cohesion Green Paper (2006) - Barca Report (2009) Cohesion Policy Objective 5 (2021) Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (2022) EU4Skills (2023)

Source: ESPON (2018), Gotella (2020) and Pazos-Vidal (2023).

Rather than seeking to frame a new explicit EU competence on urban matters, the existing urban *acquis* should be codified to provide more consistency, transparency, and visibility.

A new EU power for housing?

The Conference on the Future of Europe asked for more explicit EU powers on housing and has become a key topic during this term. Therefore the political climate for an explicit EU competence on housing, on the back of the EU [Affordable Housing Plan](#), one of the present Commission’s landmark initiatives, is much more positive at the moment.

That said, a new explicit EU shared competence on housing will have the same constraints as at present:

unless the EU budget increases significantly, most of the investment to expand and renovate the housing stock will come from domestic public authorities and the private sector, for the needs far exceeds the size of the EU Budget (Multi-Annual Financial Framework, MFF). The role of the EU is and seems likely to remain, as noted by Housing Commissioner Jørgensen's Mission Letter of mobilising the internal market: to eliminating barriers to pan EU investment in housing, sustaining a favourable state aid framework, create standards for planning, building and regenerating existing housing stock.

Advance a coordinated European Union approach towards housing by framing affordability and quality of housing as cross-cutting challenges, while respecting subsidiarity. Strengthen support mechanisms – such as the Affordable Housing Plan – through EU investment and guidance, without undermining local authority over housing policies.

A new EU agenda for (big) cities?

Though the consultation document is clear that “cities” are understood in a broad sense (anything that is non-rural), the new Agenda intended focus on cities may implicitly mean big cities, particularly for systemic and pressing challenges such as climate change. This is a concern that is more implicit than explicit in the Commission consultation draft. If so, this would affect multilevel governance, or territorial cohesion, let alone regions with legislative competences. Indeed, the creation of the EU Mission ‘Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities’ in the previous term highlights that *“Cities produce >70% of global CO2 emissions. They account for > 65% of global energy consumption; They take up only 4% of the EU's land area; Cities are home to 75% of EU citizen.”*

However, such a narrow approach is difficult to work into an EU multilevel system that has a vast range of actors involved in policymaking. Furthermore, new EU policies tend to be resisted sufficiently EU-wide buy-in.

Anchor the new EU Agenda for Cities in the principle of inclusivity and proportionality by ensuring that all urban authorities, no matter the size or capacity, have a meaningful role in EU policies and programmes. EU actions should reflect the city's actual responsibilities and capabilities, while avoiding overconcentration on larger cities.

An EU Mission approach for cities?

The vision of professor Mazzucato, from which the EU Cities Mission approach under the Von der Leyen Commission takes direct inspiration, aims to make cities drivers for big societal change.

However, the current approach could only make accommodations within the constraints of the present 2021-2027 EU Budget. The [post 2027 Multi-Annual](#)

[financial Framework \(MFF\)](#) offer offers an opportunity for a more holistic approach to deliver the Agenda for Cities under an EU Mission approach.

The EU Mission ‘Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities’ should be integrated into the overall Agenda for Cities, aligning with the new Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF).

Whatever happened to the Pact of Amsterdam?

Many observers were surprised to find the commitment for a new Agenda for Cities in Vice President Fitto's Mission Letter, as for decades there has been for decades what has been called the urban *acquis* and eventually led to the Urban Agenda for the EU (UAEU) which crystallised with the [Pact of Amsterdam](#) in 2016. This was a key milestone of an organic and iterative process spanning decades, to develop a shared European “urban *acquis*”. It is both EU and intergovernmental, with different Member States acting as policy entrepreneurs of different approaches to urban policy – and which benefits from the regular, at least bi-annual meetings of the Urban Development Group (UDG) - and the on the other hand formed through a series of initiatives led by the European Commission (Structural Funds, URBAN Community Initiative, Sustainable Urban Development URBACT). Both streams coalesced between 2011 and 2016 when the Commission Directorate-General for Regional Policy became “and Urban” Policy, and the proactiveness of the Dutch ministerial representatives in the UDG led to the preparation of the Pact of Amsterdam to that led to a new form of tripartite (EU, Member States, cities) urban partnerships for addressing EU policies affecting cities, a process that continues to this day ([Leipzig 2.0](#), [Ljubljana Accord](#)) in UAEU.

To enhance the structural coordination between the intergovernmental dimension of the EU urban *acquis* in the Urban Development Group (UDG) and the Commission services in preparing EU policies and legislation for cities, but also to expand the epistemic community to other areas and departments.

Integrating Urban Agenda in EU Better Regulation

The UAEU is essentially a multilevel territorial impact assessment Better Regulation exercise to help the EU understand the local implications of its policy choices. However, the UAEU Urban Partnerships remain marred by two key drawbacks:

The first one is self-selection bias, as only the most active and networked urban voices can get involved.

The second, is the disconnect between the urban partnerships and EU Better Regulation process whereby the Commission prepares and reviews legislation.

The Agenda for Cities should incorporate the Urban Agenda for the EU partnership structures and directly link them to the Better Regulation/ Impact Assessment processes (“UAEU for urban proofing”).

Direct EU funding for cities?

While the European Commission has tried and delivered “[One-stop-shop](#)” approaches as a way to optimise the myriad of EU funding and capacity building support for cities, “Direct funding for cities” is a rallying cry that once again has been heard in the run up for the post 2027 MFF. This is a renewed attempt to revert the mainstreaming EU URBAN Community Initiative in 2007. At the moment, first 5% and then 8% of the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) is devoted to Sustainable Urban Development. This can be used to develop and deliver strategies led by city authorities, as well as a new forms of local delivery, namely Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI) and Community-Led Local Development (CLLD). That said, for the 2021-2027 period the Structural Funds have a Policy Objective 5 devoted to local development which does not have a specific earmark other than the above-mentioned 8% in ERDF. There are even calls to go to 15% post 2027.

However, [more than 50 initiatives are currently in place for cities at EU level](#), where at least a dozen are funding and capacity building instruments. Therefore, as the Commission President notes in her most recent announcement on the post 2027 MFF, the proliferation of funding instruments has become difficult to manage or even comprehend for officials, let alone by beneficiaries. And as announced in the consultation document, a consolidation is on the way, and a number of simplification criteria are necessary whereby only instruments with genuine added value (“comply or explain”) are not only retained (“necessity check”) but they have a bigger financial allocation and become more versatile (“Swiss knife”) as proposed by the [Committee of the Regions](#), with AEIDL contributing as experts.

EU support for cities can take several shapes:

Funding for Cities:

- A.1. Funding under shared management (e.g. ESIF Sustainable Urban Development)
- A.2. Funding under direct management (e.g. Horizon Mission Cities)

Capacity Building and Networking for Cities

- B.1. EU support structures and capacity building (e.g. Urban Innovative Actions/European Urban Initiative, URBACT)
- B.1. Capacity Building under shared management (e.g. ESIF Technical Assistance)

While 8% of the new post-2027 National or Regional Partnerships (Single Plans) devoted to local development seems a reasonable baseline, it is even more important to apply the principles of “comply or explain,” “necessity check,” and “Swiss knife” approaches to consolidate existing EU funding and support instruments for cities.

One-Stop-Shop for cities?

The diversity of EU funding instruments and the challenges of consolidating them has been addressed by the recourse of “one stop shops” as a way to optimise the proliferation of instruments. Such “one-stop-shops” can be:

1. Tools for technical assistance (e.g. that available in ESIF).
2. Interactive tools (such as the EU Rural Toolkit to integrate in an interactive fashion all sources of EU funds available for rural areas).
3. Guidance consolidating in a single document all existing EU funds, including examples, such as the European Parliament Guide to EU funds.
4. Integration in a single holistic document all dispersed EU interventions across various DGs, such as the EU Rural Action Plan launched in 2022.
5. Creating a single capacity building and networking tool for cities, such as initially attempted with the [European Urban Initiative](#) (EUI).

The Long-Term Vision for rural Areas offers a template of how a comprehensive package with the 5 above strands can also look like in cities. However, the genesis of the present EUI (see Table III), which eventually did not include the URBACT programme, shows the difficulties in merging instruments.

Existing EU urban initiatives should be subject to consolidation, and be made subservient to the strategic requirements of a new EU Urban Mission directly managed by the Commission and sitting atop of the remaining instruments. This Mission will be an urban-focused one-stop shops within the Agenda for Cities to further consolidate access to EU funds, technical assistance and capacity-building tools.

Table III. Initial proposal for the EUI

Roles	Cities	Member States	European Commission	Management
URBACT (shared management)	Not represented	Strategy steering Management by one Member State	Supervision	Managing authority – secretariat CGET
Urban Innovative Actions (UIA) (indirect management)	Not represented	Not represented	Management	Entrusted entity Secretariat
Urban Agenda of the EU (UAEU) (intergovernmental process, direct management of administration)	Represented by CEMR and cities network	Supervision	Management	EC - Framework contract
Urban Development Network (UDN) (direct management)	Not represented	Not represented	Management	EC - Framework contract
EUI based on the Commission proposal (indirect management)	Strategy steering	Strategy steering	Strategy steering and management	Entrusted entity Secretariat

Source: European Commission (2019)

tool, as seen in the official reporting to the EU (known as the Voluntary Reviews), instead of a performance management instrument.

This is a missed opportunity, for SDGs and in particular SDG11 has acted as a mobilising device for structural reforms and good governance in some Member States particularly sensitive to the SDG agenda, without the significant resources of 8% of Sustainable Urban Development ERDF earmark or the extensive capacity building support of the Covenant of Mayors.

Furthermore, given the emphasis in performance management, outcome-based policies, and finance not linked to costs but to structural reforms that will be the key features of the post 2027 EU budget, mainstreaming SDG11 through an ambitious performance management mechanism sitting within the Agenda for Cities (including making it an enabling condition to receive Sustainable Urban Development funding) can be act a positive catalyst for change and show EU leadership in urban sustainability worldwide.

SDG11 should be mainstreamed as a performance management tool within the Agenda for Cities, making it an enabling condition to receive Sustainable Urban Development funding.

Agenda for Cities delivering SDG11

Last but not least, while the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was already a commitment in the previous Commission, the Von der Leyen Commission has [mainstreamed SDG into EU policymaking](#), as outlined in the respective Mission Letters. This includes SDG11 on Sustainable Cities and Communities.

That said, and the EU is not alone in this, the SDGs are considered essentially as a performance reporting

Conclusion

This Policy Brief sums up some of the emerging ideas that AEIDL is considering for the future of urban areas and indeed urban-rural linkages on the back of the, [RURBANIVE](#) project as the European Commission is preparing both the new Agenda For Cities but also the next post 2027 EU Budget. AEIDL will continue working on formulating EU policy ideas based on evidence from our research from this and other projects such as [BEATLES](#), [SMART ERA](#), [FUTURAL](#), [RURACTIVE](#).

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